

IMPROVEMENT OF THE TRANSPORT SYSTEM OF SHAHRISABZ CITY BASED ON INTELLIGENT MICROSCOPIC MODELLING

Karimov Akmal Akbarovich

PhD in Technical Sciences,

Associate Professor, Karshi State Technical University, Karshi,
Uzbekistan.

Makhmudov Zukhriddin Nuriddinovich

master's student in Transport Engineering. Karshi State Technical
University, Karshi, Uzbekistan.

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyzes the transport system of Shahrissabz city, focusing on traffic flows, infrastructure, and key issues of public transport operation. Using intelligent microscopic modelling, traffic flow assessment and forecasting are carried out. Practical recommendations are developed to improve efficiency, safety, and reduce traffic congestion.

Introduction. In the 21st century, rapid urbanization has made the efficient organization of urban transport systems a matter of global importance. According to the United Nations, approximately 57% of the world's population currently lives in urban areas, and this figure is projected to reach 68% by 2050. This process creates new challenges related to increasing load on urban road-transport infrastructure, rising traffic congestion, worsening environmental problems, and ensuring population mobility. Therefore, in developed countries, particular attention is paid to transport master planning, priority development of public transport, implementation of digital management systems, and modeling of transport flows.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, in recent years, large-scale reforms have been implemented to modernize transport infrastructure, provide high-quality and safe transport services, introduce modern bus routes in regions, and improve urban mobility. The gradual increase in urbanization across the country, along with the expansion of new residential areas, industrial zones, educational and service facilities, necessitates a scientifically grounded revision of transport systems. In particular, improving public transport networks in regional cities remains one of the most urgent issues.

Shahrissabz city is one of the major historical, tourist, and socio-economic centers of the Kashkadarya region. Due to the continuous growth of the population, expansion of tourism flows, and development of new residential and service areas, the demand for transport services in the city has increased significantly. However, for a long time, modern bus routes were not sufficiently developed in the city, and the population has largely relied on small-

capacity minibuses and private vehicles, which has led to several problems in the existing transport system.

In particular, low quality and irregularity of passenger transport services, lack of scientifically based route network planning, reduced capacity at certain streets and intersections, occurrence of traffic congestion, increased environmental load, and insufficient satisfaction of the population's need for convenient and safe transport services have been observed.

Under these conditions, developing a transport master plan for Shahrissabz city, conducting a comprehensive assessment of the existing transport situation, analyzing passenger flows, modeling problematic intersections using modern software tools, and scientifically substantiating new bus routes are considered urgent scientific and practical tasks.

The objective of the study is to comprehensively investigate the current state of the road-transport system in Shahrissabz city, determine the population's demand for transport services, and develop a transport master plan for the city based on modern modeling methods, including the scientific justification of new bus routes and the development of transport flow models.

To achieve this objective, the following tasks were addressed:

- studying theoretical and methodological approaches to urban transport system planning;
- analyzing the current state of Shahrissabz city's road-transport infrastructure;
- assessing the technical condition and capacity of the urban street-road network;
- conducting surveys among the population based on age, gender, and social status regarding transport usage;
- studying urban transport and passenger flows through field observations;
- analyzing passenger transportation conditions on existing minibus (Damas) routes;
- identifying problematic intersections and modeling them using PTV VISSIM software;
- developing optimal solutions for improving traffic conditions;
- scientifically substantiating new bus routes and developing transport models;
- evaluating the socio-economic effectiveness of the proposed measures.

The research object includes the road-transport system of Shahrissabz city, the urban street-road network, public transport infrastructure, and passenger transportation processes.

The research subject covers organizational, technical, and economic relations arising in the process of managing transport flows, improving passenger transport systems, forming public transport routes, increasing intersection capacity, and developing a transport master plan in Shahrissabz city.

The scientific novelty of the study includes the following:

- A multi-layer model was developed for assessing transport demand by integrating behavioral characteristics of the population, time-dependent dynamics, spatial accessibility, and empirical weights based on real passenger flow data within existing multi-criteria approaches. As a result, an applied algorithm for transport demand assessment in the conditions of Shahrissabz city was formed.

• A calibrated simulation model of Shahrizabz city traffic intersections was developed in the PTV VISSIM environment based on real field observations and time-motion data. This enabled the justification of decision-making approaches aimed at optimizing traffic flows. Dynamic traffic parameters were identified based on field measurements, and management decisions were formulated to minimize delays through optimization of intersection operating regimes.

In recent years, significant scientific and practical attention has been given to traffic flow modeling. Such modeling is aimed at describing and analyzing traffic behavior, and it has become particularly important due to the widespread occurrence of congestion in urban areas.

Traffic congestion occurs when the road capacity is lower than the traffic flow demand. As a result, disruptions in traffic flow emerge, leading to congestion and reduced efficiency of movement. Therefore, the use of high-precision traffic models allows the system efficiency to be improved by bringing traffic flow dynamics closer to real-world conditions.

To describe traffic flow, three main approaches are used: microscopic, macroscopic, and mesoscopic models. Microscopic models take into account the behavior of individual vehicles and analyze parameters such as their position, speed, time headway, and spacing. These models are used to predict traffic dynamics based on drivers' psychological and physical reactions.

Macroscopic models consider traffic flow as a whole system and analyze aggregate characteristics such as average speed, density, and flow rate. Mesoscopic models, on the other hand, combine microscopic and macroscopic approaches and operate at the level of vehicle groups using probabilistic methods.

Early microscopic models linked vehicle speed to the distance between the leading and following vehicles; however, they were unable to fully represent real traffic flow behavior. Later approaches introduced relationships between density and speed, but these often resulted in unrealistic acceleration patterns and non-physical behavior.

The Newell model and its improved versions also failed to fully capture traffic dynamics due to insufficient consideration of speed differences. Subsequent studies developed models incorporating reaction to speed variations; however, these often led to overly aggressive acceleration behavior.

Comprehensive analyses show that further improvement of traffic flow models is necessary. One of the key directions is adaptive flow control based on predicted traffic conditions. This study aims to describe traffic behavior in a more realistic and accurate manner.

The Euler method is used in evaluating traffic models. It is a simple yet effective numerical technique for solving systems of differential equations and is widely applied in traffic simulation. This method divides time into discrete steps and approximates the position, speed, and acceleration of vehicles at each step based on the model.

The change in distance with respect to time leads to a change in velocity, which can be expressed as follows:

$$v = dS/dt, \quad (1.1)$$

The change in velocity with respect to time leads to acceleration, which can be expressed as follows:

$$a = dv/dt, \quad (1.2)$$

or, in other words, acceleration is equal to the time derivative of velocity.

In transport models, using the Euler method, position (location) and velocity are expressed in the following form:

$$S_F^{x+1} = S_F^x + \Delta t \times v_F^x \quad (1.3)$$

$$v_F^{x+1} = v_F^x + \Delta t \times a \quad (1.4)$$

Here, in the Euler discrete-time model, the notations are defined as follows:

here, x represents the current time step, and $x+1$ represents the next time step.

S_F^x , v_F^x and a_F^x respectively, they denote the position, velocity, and acceleration of the following vehicle at time interval x , where

$$t = x\Delta t \quad (1.5)$$

and Δt — and represents the time step duration.

When the traffic model is unstable, small disturbances within the traffic flow increase over time. Conversely, when the model is stable, these disturbances gradually diminish, and the flow returns to a smooth state.

In traffic flow theory, two main types of stability are particularly important: local stability and string (or chain) stability.

In local stability, small fluctuations increase over time both in amplitude and in the number of affected vehicles, and the system does not return to its equilibrium state. In other words, when local instability occurs, the traffic flow does not recover its previous equilibrium, which is considered a negative condition.

String (chain) stability means that disturbances in the traffic flow may temporarily amplify; however, all vehicles eventually return to their initial equilibrium state. This type of stability is directly related to stop-and-go waves.

In other words, if the model is not string stable, small disturbances grow over time, and after propagating through several vehicles, nonlinear effects emerge. As a result, stop-and-go waves appear in the traffic flow.

Stop-and-go traffic refers to a situation in which vehicles repeatedly accelerate and decelerate, causing multiple cycles of stopping and moving again. This phenomenon leads to the formation of traffic congestion.

The reason for this is that when a driver accelerates, traffic density increases upstream and speed decreases downstream. Similarly, when a driver suddenly brakes, the resulting disturbance propagates upstream, leading to the formation of stop-and-go waves.

This paper examines driver reaction and sensitivity characteristics in describing traffic flow behavior. In congestion conditions, “stop-and-go” waves cause frequent changes in vehicle speed, which reduce the overall efficiency of traffic flow. The spacing between vehicles and time headway significantly influence driver reaction and can lead to noticeable variations in traffic flow behavior.

The time headway τ is defined as the time required for a driver to adapt to the state of the leading vehicle. The distance traveled during this time is referred to as the spacing (headway distance). Adaptation in traffic flow refers to the process of adjusting speed in response to changes in the movement of the vehicle ahead.

A driver reacts more slowly when the spacing is large and more quickly when the spacing is small. In addition, driver response depends on sensitivity, which is assumed to be proportional to changes in speed.

Since driver reaction is not uniform under all traffic conditions, these factors must be taken into account in models to ensure an accurate and realistic description of traffic flow.

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